

fish whose initial population was 37,500 increased in number by 209%; in size, each fish increased by 4 cm. Fish weight

increased considerably during the cropping duration. A higher population reduced the ultimate size of each

individual fish and the total fish yield per hectare. But fish culture had no appreciable effect on the rice yield. ■

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Suitable cultivars for intensive rice-based cropping systems in Bangladesh

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The Rice Cropping Systems Division initiated research to evaluate and modify the essentially rice-based cropping systems of the BRRI project area. The cultivation of nonrice crops should be incorporated into the existing rice cropping systems to improve the potential cropping patterns for rainfed and irrigated areas. Unfortunately, suitable cultivars for many nonrice crops were not available from local sources. BRRI has no mandate to develop varieties other than those of rice, so the division undertook a

Promising cultivars for intensive rice-based multiple cropping systems. BRRI, Bangladesh.

Crops	Best performing cultivars	Potentially acceptable cultivars
Field corn	Thai Comp., No. 1 DMR BC ₃ (S) C1, Early DMR Comp. 2	Thai Comp., No. 1 (S) C ₂ , Early DMR Comp. 1
Sweet corn	Thai Comp. supersweet DMR #1	College sweet synthetic
Sorghum	IS2940, Cosor 2	CS108, Cosor 3, CS100
Pearl millet	ICRISAT-7141NEP-13-5007-2 (OP)	ICRISAT-7142NEP-13-5613-1 (OP)
Peanut	Kidang, SK-38	CES101, P23, EG. Bunchy
Soybean	Davis, Williams (dry season) Bossier, Hardee, Seemes (wet season)	Clark 63, TK5 Williams, Davis
Chickpea	ICRISAT No. 4951, 2784	2836, 4961, 4465
Cowpea	All season	TVU354, TVU201, RDC-6-12W

varietal screening program with active participation of relevant national and international organizations.

From 1974 to 1978, varieties of corn, sorghum, pearl millet, peanut, soybean, cowpea, and chickpea were evaluated at

the BRRI experimental farms and in selected farmers' fields of the BRRI project area. Several promising varieties were identified (see table) and are now used in various single and double cropping systems in the area. ■

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Evaluation of mung bean cultivars under monoculture and intercropping systems

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The pulse crop mung bean *Vigna radiata* is grown mostly as monoculture but is

also intercropped with corn and sugarcane or grown under plantation crops such as coconut or rubber. Mung bean is also relayed in wetland rice in most of Southeast Asia. Evaluation of mung bean varieties for varied conditions is imperative because of yield fluctuations due to seasonal and environmental situations. An important question is whether breeders should evaluate varieties

in monoculture or in intercropping systems for maximum testing efficiency.

Ten mung bean varieties were evaluated in monoculture and intercropped with corn in dry- and wet-season trials in 1978-79 at the new upland area of the IRRI experimental farm. Recommended cultural management practices, such as fertilization, weeding, irrigation, and

Yield comparison (kg/ha) of mung bean varieties and their relative ranking for monoculture and when intercropped with corn. IRRI, 1978-79 dry season and 1979 wet season.^a

Mung bean variety	1978-79 dry season				1979 wet season			
	Monoculture yield (kg/ha)	Rank	Intercrop yield (kg/ha)	Rank	Monoculture yield (kg/ha)	Rank	Intercrop yield (kg/ha)	Rank
EG-MG-174-3	850 a	1	203	2	873 abc	5	465 abc	6
CES 55	638 ab	2	213	1	779 bc	8	377 c	8
S8 (Green)	619 b	3	160	5	671 c	10	363 c	9
M350	601 b	4	135	7	1055 a	2	525 abc	4
CES-1T-2	589 b	5	178	3	1061 a	1	667 a	1
CES-14	561 b	6	137	6	821 abc	7	387 bc	7
CES-U-1	534 b	7	168	4	694 c	9	315 c	10
MG-50-10A (Y)	490 b	8	115	10	1024 ab	3	478 abc	5
CES-1D-21	475 b	9	127	9	877 abc	4	611 a	2
CES-1F-5	449 b	10	129	8	871 abc	6	598 ab	3
Mean	580		157 ns		873		478	
CV (%)	23		42		18		21	

^ans = not significant. In a column means followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at the 5% level.